

**Synthesis in Coumarino-pyrone and Furocoumarin Groups.
Part II. Synthesis of 3,4'-Dimethyl-8'-ethyl-5',6'-
furocoumarin and 3,2'-Dimethyl-3'-acetyl-8'-
ethyl-5',6'-furochromone**

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3-Methyl-5-ethyl-6-hydroxy-7-acetylcoumarone, prepared from 3-bromo-4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylm-belliferone by Fittig and Ebert's reaction, has been used for the synthesis of 3,4'-dimethyl-8'-ethyl-5',6'-furocoumarin and 3,2'-dimethyl-3'-acetyl-8'-ethyl-5',6'-furochromone by the Kostanecki acylation method.

Furocoumarins and furochromones can be prepared by building a furane ring on coumarins and chromones¹ respectively or by building an α - or γ -pyrone ring on coumarones². The latter method has been adopted for the synthesis of a furocoumarin and a furochromone from 3-methyl-5-ethyl-6-hydroxy-7-acetylcoumarone(III).

The necessary coumarone was prepared by Fittig and Ebert's reaction³ from 3-bromo-4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylm-belliferone (I) or by decarboxylation of 3-methyl-5-ethyl-6-hydroxy-7-acetylcoumarilic acid (II), which was obtained by hydrolysis of 3-bromo-4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylm-belliferone with NaOH solution.

The coumarone (III) was subjected to the Kostanecki acylation and the resulting solid on crystallisation melted indefinitely between 140° and 150°. By Wittig's method⁴, a furocoumarin (IV), m.p. 185°, was isolated.

Condensation of 3-methyl-5-ethyl-6-hydroxycoumarone⁵ with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of H₂SO₄ furnished the furocoumarin, m.p. 185°, identical with the one prepared by the Kostanecki acylation (*vide supra*). This has been represented as 3, 4'-dimethyl-8'-ethyl-5',6'-furocoumarin (IV), as confirmed by its solubility in boiling NaOH solution and regeneration with acid.

The furocoumarin (IV) on being subjected to simultaneous hydrolysis and methylation furnished a monobasic acid, m.p. 155°, formulated as 2-methoxy-3-ethyl-6, 5-(3'-methylfuro)- β -methylcinnamic acid(VI).

In order to separate the furochromone from the mixture, m.p. 140-50°, fractional crystallisation was used. Sulphuric ether caused a partial separation of the mixture. The fraction, more insoluble in ether, was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol when a product, m.p. 172°, was obtained. This compound has the composition C₁₇H₁₆O₄ as com

1. Limaye, *Ber.*, 1932, 65, 375; *Rasayanam*, 1936, 1, 1; 1939, 1, 187; Shah and Shah, *this Journal*, 1949, 17, 41.

2. Limaye and Sathe, *Rasayanam*, 1937, 1, 87.

3. *Annalen*, 1863, 216, 163.

4. *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 88.

5. Limaye and Thakar, *Marathwada Univ., J.*, 1963, 3, 116.

pared with $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ for the expected furochromone. This suggests the possible presence of an acetyl group in the compound, m.p. 172° , as confirmed by formation of a 2,4-D.N.P. in almost quantitative yield, m.p. 251° . Its structure was also confirmed by the products of hydrolysis. This compound on hydrolysis with NaOH solution provided (a) an acid, m.p. 192° (decomp.) and (b) 3-methyl-5-ethyl-6-hydroxy-7-acetylcoumarone (III), an *ortho*-hydroxyketone. The acid, m.p. 192° , on decarboxylation yielded 3-methyl-5-ethyl-6-hydroxycoumarone (VIII)⁵. This acid is therefore represented as 3-methyl-5-ethyl-6-hydroxycoumarone-7-carboxylic acid (VII), a salicylic acid type of compound. The formation of *o*-hydroxy-acid (VII) and *o*-hydroxy-ketone (III) confirms the furochromone structure for the compound, m.p. 172° . This compound is therefore formulated as 3,2'-dimethyl-3'-acetyl-8'-ethyl-5',6'-furochromone (V).

The furochromone (v), on hydrolysis with Na_2CO_3 solution, could not be deacetylated, which is rather unusual.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

(VII)

(VIII)

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Bromo-4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylcoumarone (I). — To 4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylcoumarone⁶ (24.6 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (120 ml), was added a 25% solution of bromine in acetic acid (64 ml). Fumes of HBr were liberated; a crystalline precipitate

6. Limaye and Limaye, *Rasayanam*, 1941, 1, 201.

appeared after 2 hr. It was repeatedly crystallised from glacial acetic acid in rectangular plates, m.p. 172°, yield 22 g. (Found: Br, 24.31. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4Br$ requires Br, 24.61%).

The *acetate* of (I) was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 160°. (Found: Br, 21.45. $C_{16}H_{15}O_3Br$ requires Br, 21.80%).

3-Methyl-5-ethyl-6-hydroxy-7-acetylcoumarilic Acid (II).—The compound (I, 54 g.) was refluxed with 2*N*-NaOH (45 ml) for ½ hr. The solution, formed on acidification, provided a solid, which was crystallised from 60% acetic acid in rectangular reddish plates, m.p. 225° (decomp.), yield 3 g. (Found: C, 63.21; H, 5.25. $C_{14}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 64.12; H, 5.34%).

3-Methyl-5-ethyl-6-hydroxy-7-acetylcoumarone (III): *Method I*.—3-Methyl-5-ethyl-6-hydroxy-7-acetylcoumarilic acid was heated above its m.p. for half an hour. Some of the decarboxylated substance sublimed during heating. The reaction mass was crystallised from 40% ethanol, m.p. 60°.

Method II.—On refluxing compound (I, 1 g.) with 10% Na_2CO_3 solution (15 ml) for 2 hr., the reaction mixture was filtered and acidified. The resulting precipitate was crystallised from 40% ethanol in silky needles, m.p. 60°. It showed a greenish ferric chloride reaction. (Found: C, 71.50; H, 6.31. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.55; H, 6.42%).

The *acetate* of (III) was crystallised from 30% acetic acid in long, colorless, thin needles, m.p. 59°. (Found: C, 68.80; H, 6.09. $C_{13}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 69.23; H, 6.15%).

3,4'-Dimethyl-8'-ethyl-5',6'-furocoumarin (IV).—3-Methyl-5-ethyl-6-hydroxy-7-acetylcoumarone (5 g.), fused sodium acetate (5 g.), and acetic anhydride (10 ml) were heated at 160-65° for 30 hr., adding acetic anhydride (1 ml) after each 6 hr. The reaction mass was poured on crushed ice and the resulting solid was crystallised from 60% ethanol, m.p. 140-50°, yield 1.5 g.

The above crude product was refluxed with 2*N*-NaOH solution for 1½ hr. to rupture α - and γ -pyrone rings present in the furocoumarin and the furochromone. The precipitate, formed by acidification of the solution, was filtered and treated with excess of *N*-NaOH solution to dissolve the acid formed from the furochromone. Major portion of the solid went into solution. The residue was crystallised from 50% acetic acid in shining yellowish needles, m.p. 185°, yield 0.1 g. It was insoluble in cold NaOH solution, but on boiling dissolved to an orange solution from which it could be recovered on acidification. (Found: C, 74.04; H, 5.66. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 74.39; H, 5.79%).

By Pechmann Reaction.—To 3-methyl-5-ethyl-6-hydroxycoumarone (5 g.), dissolved in acetoacetic ester (40 ml), H_2SO_4 (conc., 5 ml) was slowly added. The reaction mixture was kept for a weak. Half of the acetoacetic ester was evaporated when a solid separated. It was filtered, washed with dilute NaOH solution, and again with water. It was crystallised from 50% acetic acid, m.p. 185°. Mixed m.p. with 3,4'-dimethyl-8'-ethyl-5',6'-furocoumarin, prepared above by the Kostanecki method, showed no depression.

2-Methoxy-3-ethyl-6,5-(3'-methylfuro)- β -methylcinnamic Acid (VI).—The furocoumarin (IV, 1 g.) was dissolved in 2*N*-NaOH solution (8 ml) by boiling and dimethyl sulphate (5 ml) was added to the hot solution. The mixture was refluxed for 1 hr. It was then acidified. The resulting precipitate was extracted with $NaHCO_3$ solution and

the extract was acidified when a precipitate was formed. This was crystallised from 60% ethanol, m.p. 155°, yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 69.63; H, 6.52; equiv., 270.4. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 70.06; H, 6.57%; equiv., 274).

3,2'-Dimethyl-3'-acetyl-8'-ethyl-5',6'-furochromone (V).—The above crude product (3 g.), m.p. 140-50°, was extracted with ether (150 ml), using 15 ml each time. On evaporating the ether a product, m.p. 120-25°, was obtained. This product yielded by Wittig's method the furocoumarin, m.p. 185°.

The residue left after ether extraction was crystallised from ethanol in short, reddish needles, m.p. 172°, yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 71.53; H, 5.47. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.83; H, 5.63%). This compound could not be deacetylated by boiling with Na_2CO_3 solution.

2,4-DNP of 3,2'-Dimethyl-3'-acetyl-8'-ethyl-5',6'-furochromone.—3,2'-Dimethyl-3'-acetyl-8'-ethyl-5',6'-furochromone (0.01 g.) was dissolved in aldehyde-free ethanol and excess of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine solution was added to the hot ethanolic solution. The reaction mixture was kept overnight when an orange precipitate of 2,4-DNP gradually separated. The solid was filtered, washed with 5*N*-HCl, and dried; m.p. 251°, yield 0.01978 g. (% Carbonyl group found: 11.76; expected 9.97). (Found: N, 11.92. $C_{23}H_{20}O_7N_4$ requires N, 12.07%).